

MILITARY EXPENDITURE EVALUATION: EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE FROM ALBANIA**Llesh Lleshaj,***PhD in Statistics, lecturer at Faculty of Economy, University of Tirana, Albania***Vilson Lleshaj***Active NCO at Special Operations Regiment, Armed Forces, Albania***Abstract**

Purpose of the research: Even though military investments are considered capital expenditures that do not motivate the private sector, it gives special importance to national security or defense by preventing various military aggressions, terrorism, border defending, and whole global peace. As a consequence, military spending constitutes a very peculiar category of public expenditure. Motivating by this fact, the article deals with an empirical investigation of the determinants of military expenditures of Albania. *Design/methodology:* The statistical approach used is a general multiple regression model, in order to analyse the economic environment as a determinant of military expenditure, by choosing independent variables: Gross Domestic Production (GDP); Trade; Government Expenses; and Population. *Results/findings:* Processing time-series data (2002 - 2020) for Albania, it is revealed that except for government expenses all other variables are statistically significant in determining the military expenditure. In addition, the study found out only a positive correlation with GDP, and all the others are negatively correlated. *Practical implications and Conclusions:* The article demonstrated the empirical impacts that ought to be taken into consideration by the government to make decisions for further incentives in analyzing and developing military investment. The research provides empirical results encouraging further investigations on the subject matter.

Keywords: Military expenditure; economic factors, statistical approach.

1. Introduction

In recent years, spending on military investment is increased and has been affected by political developments and conflicts in some global regions. The higher level of military expenditure regarding global countries are: the United States, China, India, Russia, and the United Kingdom. In 2020, these countries together made up around 62% of global military spending (SIPRI, 2021). Understandably, these large public investments in the military industry have a significant impact on the economies of the respective countries. Of course these capital expenditures do not motivate the private sector (even exclude it) and they can be considered costs for the country's citizens and entrepreneurs. Nevertheless, in many cases, dominate the national security of various military aggressions, terrorism, protection of the territorial borders and global peace (such as NATO). There are many criticisms of military investment in many countries, the most important of which are:

- Citizens and entrepreneurs argue that every dollar spent on defense is a dollar not spent in another sector or other public service that the country may have a strong need.

- Citizens and small and medium entrepreneurs argue that every dollar spent in the military ends up in the private sector, in multinational corporations by favoring only this type of entrepreneurship (conditioned by the specifics required by the military).

- Although military development has been accompanied by an increase in technological and engineering innovations (which promotes innovation in the economy as a whole), in many cases it has been like an obstacle for the development of civil technology.

- Military investments are the premise of inciting conflicts except protecting territory, so such investments instead of being channeled for new development initiatives are spent on emergency relief and rehabilitation operations from the aftermath of military attacks.

- In many studies are identified direct and indirect correlations between military spending, the arms market, violent conflicts, reducing the potential (or available) resources for economic and social development of countries.

- In addition to those mentioned above, the production and use of weapons prevents the development and sustainable environment protection, increases the gap of property inequality, increases the level of poverty, etc.

The arms trade is continuously a flourishing industry, which in the name of security and the protection of state sovereignty territory, have often turned to the narrow interests of the policies of certain governments and corporations, by initiating violent conflicts in many regions (or by supporting them). Armed conflicts, constant threats of military attack, terrorism, etc. are the main cause for increased military spending and increased militarism. These and many others are the reason for the immediate increase in military spending, leading to instability in many aspects of public finances and the well-being of citizens, slowing down the development of social programs, education, transport, business and tourism, etc. In these circumstances, are required new additional natural resources to meet the other needs of the economy. SIPRI (2021) has warned that growing competition for natural resources “may lead to increased military spending as a means of protecting resources from internal or external threats, while resource revenues are often a source of funding for arms purchases.”

The debate over military spending is not of recent decades, Adam Smith (father of free-market economics) himself argues that the main function of government/state is to protect the nation and the ability to guarantee it at any time through the military. The governments of many countries, strategic alliances, foreign policies, etc. are faced with the dilemma of the optimal level of military investment. On the one hand, the increased attention to military investments has created imbalances in investments or scientific and technological studies against many unexpected circumstances that threaten people's lives such as natural disasters, humanitarian crises, global warming, environmental pollution, pandemics, etc.

However, in March 2022, was shown the importance of military investment in territorial defense, the case of Russia's attack on Ukraine. This event, which could provoke the start of the Third World War,

showed the importance of strategic and logistical investments in the defense of the territory and sovereignty of each country. In this context, military alliances, military investments in the new technologies and increasing the weight of these investments in relation to GDP is a necessity, as long as there are autocratic, dictatorial and fundamentalist leaders in many countries. The year 2022 is a turning point to review the efficiency and need for military investment in many countries. Many NATO members are reviewing their growing budgets for military spending, led by Germany, which has decided that military investment will be 2% of GDP starting this year.

The paramount interest is the initial analysis of the military expenditure trend as a percentage of GDP in South-Eastern Europe Countries. These results are shown in figure 1 below:

Figure 1: Trendline of military expenditure (% of GDP), Southeastern Europe Countries, 2011-2020

Source: World Bank data, proceeding by authors in Excel.

Note: ALB – Albania, EU - European Union, WLD – World, BGR – Bulgaria, BIH - Bosnia and Herzegovina, CYP – Cyprus, GRC – Greece, HRV – Croatia, MDA – Moldova, MKD - North Macedonia, MNE – Montenegro, ROU – Romania, SRB – Serbia, SVN – Slovenia, TUR – Turkey, and XKX – Kosovo.

In the last decade, as shown in figure 1, Albania is very close to the level of military expenditure compared to the European Union, but very below the global average percentage. However compared to Southeastern Europe Countries, Albania invests more in the military (as% of GDP) than no-NATO countries: Moldova, Kosovo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and NATO countries Slovenia, and North Macedonia.

Taking everything into consideration, focus on the importance of the military especially in the last years, we are motivated to do such a study that does not exist yet for Albania. The statistical approach used in this study is a general multiple regression model, in order to analyze the economic environment as a determinant of military expenditure, by choosing independent variables with hypothesis: “Factors like gross domestic product growth, international trade, government expenses, and population determine the military expenditure scale in Albania.”

2. Literature review

Military expenditure as a public investment has several positive effects on capital, labor, growth, and the effectual use of available resources in the economy as a whole (Lobont et al., 2019). There are many studies that estimate the military expenditure effects on economic growth and viceversa. Some selected studies regarding the type of economic factors and cross-countries that affect military expenditure are mentioned below:

Gross domestic product impact on military expenditure and vice-versa: Dunne and Uye (2013) survey 102 studies and found out positive effect of the military expenditure on the economic growth about 20% of the cross-country, and negative effect about 35% of the case. However, in study by Yakovlev (2007) concluded that military spending and net arms exports have negative impacts on economic growth but their interaction has a positive impact on growth. Proceeding panel

data for 23 countries, Chang et al. (2011) an investigated exogenous effect the military expenditure and its effect on economic growth, according to this study they found out a threshold limit of economic growth, that below this limit there is a negative relationship between the two variables, whereas when the income increases above the threshold limit exist a positive cointegration. In addition, Raju and Ahmed conducted (2019) between these two variables there is a positive long-run relationship (using cointegration and causality test). The economic effect of military expenditure is an essential issue for the developing world. The impact of military expenditure on the growth, for a set of 35 countries from non-OECD over 1988–2019, by applying the Granger causality test exposes bidirectional causal effect between military expenses and economic growth (Muhammad Azam, 2020). An interesting study by (Odehna et al. 2021) analyzed the relationship between the military expenditure of NATO member countries (as dependent variable) and selected dependent variables: gross domestic product, government expenditure (non-military), the share of trade balance of gross domestic product, and population. Applying Autoregressive Distributed Lag model found out: (1) in the short-term results demonstrate follower behaviour, especially in the new NATO member states (an effort to fulfill the commitment to spend 2% of the gross domestic product on defense); (2) in the long-term results have revealed a positive relationship between military expenditure and gross domestic product.

General government expenses impact on military expenditure: From the official publications of Eurostat, general government expenditure in the Europe Union on defence amounted to 1.2 % of GDP in 2019. Around the world, countries with the highest military spending

worldwide in 2020, are United States, China, India, Russia, and United Kingdom. The only United States has about 39% percent of the total military spending worldwide this year (SIPRI, 2021). According to a study conducted in 2020 by Odehna and Neubauer, by analyzing NATO countries, they revealed a strong negative correlation with statistical significance between military expenditure and other government expending. Such a phenomenon is expected to occur because increased investment in the military leads to less investment in other civil sectors.

International trade impact on military expenditure: The larger expansion in the demand country's tradable commodities in international trade the more can impact defense spending. There are studies such as opening economy to international trade leads to greater resources being diverted towards the military sector (Seiglie, 2016).

Population growth impact on military expenditure: Last two decades, army forces are getting smaller relative to the civilian population, but in absolute terms, they stay at a fairly constant level (Roser and Nagdy, 2013). According to this study, the army forces personnel across countries and world regions has a negative trend, as well hold this if we observe the army forces as a share of the labor force.

3. Research methodology

3.1 Data sample and stationarity

The analysis of this study is based on annual frequency of time series data from 2002 to 2020 (the selected period is conditioned by official data). The meaning of the variables in the model and their description as well as the source of information is shown in Tab. 1:

Table 1

Meaning of variables and descriptive statistics

Abbreviation	Description of the variable	Average value	Std. deviation
Dependent variable:			
MEXP	Military expenditure (current USD)	1.6E+08	50096812
Independent variable:			
GDP	Gross Domestic Production (current US\$)	1.13E+10	3.12E+09
POP	Population (total number)	2929360	66673.97
TR	Trade (% of GDP)	74.1	5.33
GE	Government Expenses (% of GDP)	23.64	0.56

Source: World Bank data and author's summary, 2020 and authors' calculation in EViews 12.

To get an efficient model, we must first check the variables' stationarity using ADF Test of Unit Root (Dickey and Fuller, 1979). This test is fundamental to testing the series and return it to a stationary series. To perform this, we have used the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test (ADF). The basic equation of the ADF test linked with the constant and the trend (first-order integral) is:

$$\Delta X_t = \lambda_0 + \lambda_1 t + \lambda_2 X_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \lambda_i \Delta X_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

The first difference $\Delta X_t = X_t - X_{t-1}$ in the period t , where λ_0 is the constant and t is the trend, with the null hypothesis, $H_0: \lambda_2 = 0$ (time series data is non-stationary).

3.2 Multiple linear regression

After the stationarity process our study will perform and estimate the linear model as follow:

$$MEXP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GDP_t + \beta_2 POP_t + \beta_3 TR_t + \beta_4 GE_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

Which explain these meaning:

β_i - model parameters, or coefficients of independent variables in the model, for $i = 1, \dots, 4$ (in this study, the change of the dependent variable $\Delta MEXP$ is explained by these coefficients β_i when Δ independent variable = + 1 unit, "ceteris paribus").

ε_t - is called regression residual or error term, it is the only variable that is not provided or is not explained by the model and it should be stochastic. This error term is known as the statistical error of the model (it is a

community of other influencing factors not included in the model).

Estimating parameters β_i it will be used the ordinary least squares method, this means that we need to minimize the square of errors. To make the parameter evaluation, it will be used the ordinary least square method (Dougherty, 2007). This evaluation set up conclusions with high statistical reliability, we will rely on all the basic assumptions of the Gauss-Markov theorem (Wooldridge, 2016). According to this theorem, as a re-

gression model should be statistically the best and useful for economic analysis it must meet certain assumption: (1) linear in parameters; (2) random sampling; (3) no perfect collinearity; (4) zero conditional mean; (5) homoskedasticity; (6) normality.

3.3 Empirical analysis and findings

At first, through the ADF-test, time series were transformed into stationary (Table 2 shows time-series that are stationary in level, first-order stationary, or second-order stationary), and then these variables were used for parametric estimating of the multiple regression model of military expenses for Albania:

Table 2.

Time Series Stationarity Test (ADF: unite root-test)

Variable	Level		First difference		Second difference	
	t-stat.	Prob.	t-stat.	Prob.	t-stat.	Prob.
MEXP	-1.92	0.6010	-3.47	0.0200	---	---
TR	-1.72	0.7215	-3.17	0.1218	-4.94	0.0062
POP	-2.85	0.2036	-2.74	0.2368	-2.47	0.0174
GDP	-2.13	0.4959	-3.42	0.0815	-4.39	0.0173
GE	-3.29	0.0320	---	---	---	---

Source: Authors' calculation in EViews 12.

Note: I(1) shows that the series is first-order integral (i.e., it is stationary with first difference, or symbol Δ) and I(2) shows that the series is second-order integral (i.e., it is stationary with second difference, or symbol Δ^2).

Understanding the relationship (link strength and link direction) between variables, we estimated the correlation coefficients

Table 3.

Correlation matrix

	MEXP	TR	POP	GDP	GE
MEXP	1				
TR	0.4422	1			
POP	-0.6429*	-0.2588	1		
GDP	0.8295*	0.3962	-0.9371*	1	
GE	-0.2087	0.0881	0.0189	-0.1506	1

Source: Authors' calculation in EViews 12.

Note: *) for statistical significance level of $p < 5\%$.

As we can observe from Table 3, there are few correlative links of statistical significance, but what is noticeable is that military expenditure has strong and negative correlations with population size and strong and positive correlations with GDP.

According to the empirical analysis for the multiple regression model in Albania, we identify the relationship of the dependent variable military expenditure (MEXP) with the independent variables shown in the table 4.

Table 4.

Parametric Estimations of the Military Expenditure Model in Albania

Dependent variable: $\Delta MEXP_t$	Coefficient or model parameters	Probability of statistical significance
Constant	3.29E+08	0.2267
Independent variables:		
$\Delta^2 TR_t$	-1622426	0.0733**
ΔPOP_t	-1925.35	0.0322*
$\Delta^2 GDP_t$	+0.0175	0.0006*
GE_t	-14515910	0.2067
Adjusted R^2	0.6133	
F-statistic	7.3453	0.0031

Source: Authors' calculation in EViews 12.

Note: *) for statistical significance level of $p < 5\%$ and **) for statistical significance level of $p < 10\%$.

According to the Fisher test, the model is statistically significant with significance level $p < 1\%$. The model also has a satisfying determinant coefficient referring to real economies, with an adjusted value $R^2 = 61.33\%$.

Table 5.

Analysis of the Residual (Military Expenditure Model)		
The test	Description of hypothesis	Test result
Model function: Ramsey RESET-test	This test estimates if the model function is appropriate or not. Null hypothesis: "the function of the model is linear"	Ramsey RESET test suggests the linear form of the model (with statistical significance level $p < 1\%$)
Multicollinearity: VIF-test (Variance Inflation Factors)	This test estimates if the independent variables are correlated with residual or error of model, ε_t . Null hypothesis: model does not have multicollinearity	According to the VIF test all independent variables are less than 10 d.m.th our model does not have multicollinearity. (this is explained by the use of time series differences to convert them to stationary).
Autocorrelation: LM-test (Breusch Godfrey)	This test estimates if the residual of the model, ε_t , has or not serial correlation. Null hypothesis: model does not have autocorrelation	Doing the autocorrelation test with two-time delays (suggested by the test itself), it figures out that our model has no autocorrelation.
Heteroskedasticity: Breusch-Pagan Godfrey-statistic	This test estimates if the residual of the model, ε_t , has or not constant variance. Null hypothesis: model does not have heteroskedasticity	According to the test null hypothesis do not reject, so the model has no heteroskedasticity.
Normality of the residual distribution ε_t : Jarque-Bera-test	This test estimates if the residual of the model, ε_t , has or not normality distribution. Null hypothesis: the residual of the model has normality distribution.	According to the test null hypothesis do not reject. So military expenditures model in Albania has no problem with normality distribution of residual, this means that model is usable and valuable to forecast in long-term.

Source: The table summarizes the tests once they were proceeded EViews 12 by the authors

This model has successfully passed all the criteria of creating efficient models according to the main assumptions of the Gauss-Markov theorem (table 5), so the model is statistically useful to explain the direction and strength correlation of the variables. Also, it has parameters and direction of correlation in relation to macroeconomic theories, as written in the empirical literature. This situation expresses that in general Military

Expenditures economy in Albania and main macroeconomic indicators have a trend like economies around the world, which shows the positive effect of GDP in the Military Expenditures.

In addition, the coefficient stability of model is tested by CUSUM of squares, that figured out a stability in long-term. This test is illustrated in figure 2 below:

Figure 2: Stability diagnostic test

Source: Authors' calculation in EViews 12.

4 Conclusion

In recent years, military expenditures are increased, driven by political developments and conflicts in some global regions. These large public investments in the military sector demotivate the private sector, they can often be considered costs for the citizens of the country and entrepreneurs. However, in many cases is paramount the national security of various military aggressions, terrorism, protection of territorial borders,

and global peace. The case of Russian aggression against the territory of Ukraine makes the analysis of the territorial defense of each state more fundamental and increases the importance of military investments.

In this study, the time series (2002 - 2020) taken into analysis for evaluating the military expenditures model shows the existence of several explanatory economic variables. According to the model, investments and military expenditures in Albania in 61% of their

performance are explained only by the four variables included in this analysis. The model analyzed as a whole is statistically significant and only one explanatory variable "Government Expenses as a percentage of GDP" is statistically insignificant. We emphasize that in Albania the level of military spending has a negative and statistically significant relationship (with a level of importance of up to 5%):

- "Total population number" is also noticed by the negative correlation coefficient between these variables. Such a connection comes for two main reasons, firstly in the last decade the population of Albania has experienced a declining male gender capable of the armed forces as a result of high emigration; secondly, the transition from compulsory to voluntary military service led to a reduction in the number of military forces according to the parameters required by NATO (2009 on going).

- "Trade as a percentage of GDP", because Albania is a developing country and has immediate needs for market development and competition in the market, always seeking the need for public infrastructure investments for trade development, in these circumstances the public budget restricts military investment by addressing funds more in the other sectors through the opening economy (international trade accounts is more important).

On the other hand, the model estimates a statistically significant and positive relationship between military spending and GDP (Gross Domestic Production), this is especially conditioned by NATO membership during the last decade, where Albania as a new member country with an economic growth trend should also increase investment in military modernization (these investments are necessary conditions that determine the level of minimum military expenditure that must be done by all members).

The estimated model has successfully passed all the assumptions of the efficient linear model to be a measurement in the long-run and short-run and helps policymakers in armed forces investment decisions, in the development and strategic plans of military investments, and all other national interest groups. Studying this field with more specific information on the composition of military investments, comparison with similar models with the countries of the Balkan Region and NATO member countries remains open scientific discussion for further research.

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"ANALYSIS OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY IN THE AGRARIAN SECTOR"

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the entrepreneurial activity in the agrarian sector, focusing on the challenges and opportunities that entrepreneurs face in this sector. The research is based on a comprehensive review of the literature on entrepreneurship in agriculture and an empirical investigation of entrepreneurs in the agrarian sector.

The research methodology involves a qualitative approach, using in-depth interviews with entrepreneurs in the agrarian sector to collect data. The data collected will be analyzed using content analysis to identify common themes and patterns in the data.

The findings of this study will provide insight into the factors that influence entrepreneurial activity in the agrarian sector, including the availability of resources, access to finance, and government policies. The study will also identify the challenges that entrepreneurs face in the agrarian sector, such as climate change, changing consumer preferences, and increasing competition.

Overall, the study will contribute to the existing literature on entrepreneurship in the agrarian sector, providing a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities that entrepreneurs face in this sector. The results of this study will be of interest to policymakers, entrepreneurs, and researchers who are interested in promoting entrepreneurship and economic development in the agrarian sector.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, agrarian sector, climate change, economic development, entrepreneurial activity, economic development.

"Analysis of the role of entrepreneurship in the agrarian sector"

Entrepreneurship plays a vital role in the agrarian sector as it is a key driver of innovation, productivity, and growth. Agricultural entrepreneurship refers to the process of creating new businesses, products, or services in the agricultural sector. It involves identifying opportunities, developing a business plan, securing funding, and launching a new venture.

One of the main benefits of agricultural entrepreneurship is that it can help to increase agricultural productivity and output. By introducing new technologies, products, and services, entrepreneurs can improve the efficiency of farming operations and enhance the quality and quantity of agricultural products.

Agricultural entrepreneurship also plays an important role in rural development. By creating new businesses and employment opportunities in rural areas, entrepreneurs can help to stimulate economic growth and reduce poverty. Additionally, entrepreneurial activities in the agrarian sector can contribute to the diversification of rural economies, reducing dependence on traditional farming activities and providing alternative income streams (Krupnik, & Thompson, 2019)..

Moreover, agricultural entrepreneurship can help to address environmental challenges facing the sector, such as climate change, soil degradation, and water scarcity. By developing innovative and sustainable farming practices, entrepreneurs can help to reduce the environmental impact of agriculture while improving the efficiency and profitability of farming operations.

Entrepreneurship is a crucial driver of growth, innovation, and sustainability in the agrarian sector. By fostering entrepreneurial activities, policymakers can create an enabling environment for the development of new businesses and the promotion of agricultural entrepreneurship. This can contribute to the growth and development of rural economies, enhance agricultural productivity and output, and promote sustainable agricultural practices.

"Factors that drive agricultural entrepreneurship"

Several factors can drive agricultural entrepreneurship. Here are some of the most important ones:

Technological advancements: Technological advancements in the agricultural sector have opened up new opportunities for agricultural entrepreneurship. For example, precision farming technologies, such as